

**PERICYTE DYSFUNCTION UNDER HYPERGLYCEMIC STRESS:
MOLECULAR IMPLICATIONS IN METABOLIC SYNDROME**

*Disfuncția pericitară sub stres hiperglicemic:
implicații moleculare în sindromul metabolic*

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Rezumat. Pericitele sunt celule murale multifuncționale, esențiale pentru menținerea integrității capilarelor și pentru reglarea tonusului vascular. În condiții de hiperglicemie acută sau cronică, așa cum se observă în sindromul metabolic, pericitele prezintă o disfuncție moleculară profundă. Aceasta include stres oxidativ și nitrozativ, fragmentare mitocondrială, autofagie afectată și activarea unor factori de transcripție proinflamatori, precum NF-κB. Pierderea consecutivă a pericitelor contribuie la instabilitatea microvasculară, la creșterea permeabilității vasculare și la hipoxia tisulară, în special în regiuni vulnerabile precum retina, pancreasul și creierul. În plus, supraexprimarea VEGF indusă de hiperglicemie agravează suplimentar dezechilibrul angiogenic și decuplarea dintre endo-

teliu și pericite. Această cercetare sintetizează dovezile actuale privind vulnerabilitatea pericitelor în sindromul metabolic, evidențiind biomarkeri timpurii și posibile ținte terapeutice pentru prevenirea complicațiilor microvasculare.

Cuvinte-cheie: pericite, hiperglicemie, sindrom metabolic, disfuncție moleculară.

Introduction

Metabolic syndrome is a global health issue, defined by a constellation of cardiovascular risk factors, including central obesity, insulin resistance, dyslipidemia, and hypertension¹. At the molecular level, hyperglycemia that is an essential component of metabolic syndrome and type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2D), has far-reaching impacts beyond the classical insulin-targeted tissues, increasingly recognized for its deleterious impact on the microvasculature².

Pericytes are mural cells that encircle the microvascular endothelium. They have emerged as main components of the microvascular architecture, playing multifaceted roles in the regulation of capillary integrity, vascular tone, maintenance of blood-brain barrier homeostasis, and angiogenesis under physiological conditions³. Their position along the capillary walls renders them extremely susceptible to metabolic disturbances, especially in the case of the ones provoked by persistent hyperglycemia in metabolic syndrome. A combination of oxidative stress (OS), advanced glycation end products (AGEs), and inflammatory cytokines contributes to pericyte dysfunction, apoptosis, and detachment from the vascular wall⁴.

The pathological outcomes of pericyte dysregulation are profound. Pericyte loss is an early preceding and predictive sign of microvascular rarefaction, capillary leakage, and fibrosis in diabetic states, and it links this pericyte subtype to the etiology of diabetic complications such as nephropathy, retinopathy, and impaired skeletal muscle glucose uptake^{3,4,6,5}. Furthermore, molecular experiments show that hyperglycemia-induced pericyte stress induces maladaptive cellular metabolism, cell proliferation, and changes in signaling path-

¹ Dhondge R.H., Agrawal S., Patil R., Kadu A., Kothari M., A Comprehensive Review of Metabolic Syndrome and Its Role in Cardiovascular Disease and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus: Mechanisms, Risk Factors, and Management, in: *Cureus*, 2024, nr. 8, e67428.

² Chilton R., Iranpour E.I., Bloomgarden Z., Deciphering the connection: Diabetes, pericyte dysfunction, and their impact on cardiovascular health, in: *Journal of Diabetes*, 2024, nr. 2, e13539; Hayden M.R., Yang Y., Habibi J., Bagree S.V., Sowers J.R., Pericytopathy: oxidative stress and impaired cellular longevity in the pancreas and skeletal muscle in metabolic syndrome and type 2 diabetes, in: *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*, 2010, nr. 5, pp. 290–303.

³ Simmonds S.J., Grootaert M.O.J., Cuijpers I., Carai P., Geuens N., Herwig M., Baatsen P., Hamdani N., Luttun A., Heymans S., Jones E.A.V., Pericyte loss initiates microvascular dysfunction in the development of diastolic dysfunction, in: *European Heart Journal Open*, 2024, vol. 4, nr. 1, art. oead129; Dabravolski S.A., Markin A.M., Andreeva E.R., Eremin I.I., Orekhov A.N., Melnichenko A.A., Emerging role of pericytes in therapy of cardiovascular diseases, in: *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 2022, vol. 156, 113928.

⁴ Simmonds S.J., Grootaert M.O.J., Cuijpers I., Carai P., Geuens N., Herwig M., Baatsen P., Hamdani N., Luttun A., Heymans S., Jones E.A.V., Pericyte loss initiates microvascular dysfunction in the development of diastolic dysfunction, in: *European Heart Journal Open*, 2024, vol. 4, nr. 1, art. oead129; Nwadozi E., Rudnicki M., Haas T.L., Metabolic Coordination of Pericyte Phenotypes: Therapeutic Implications, in: *Frontiers in Cell and Developmental Biology*, 2020, vol. 8, art. 77.

⁵ Michau A., Lafont C., Bargi-Souza P. et al., Metabolic Stress Impairs Pericyte Response to Optogenetic Stimulation in Pancreatic Islets, in: *Frontiers in Endocrinology (Lausanne)*, 2022, vol. 13, art. 918733.

ways – including enhanced oxidative stress, dysregulation of the cell cycle, and increased inflammatory signaling – that enhance microvascular injury in metabolic syndrome⁶.

Recent advances in molecular medicine have shed light on the previously underappreciated impact of pericyte dysfunction under hyperglycemic conditions, expanding our understanding of the pathobiochemical processes that drive microvascular complications in metabolic syndrome. This is why, this review has the aim to synthesize current researches on the impact of hyperglycemia on pericyte dysfunction.

Materials and methods

A comprehensive review was conducted to elucidate the molecular mechanisms underlying pericyte dysfunction under hyperglycemic stress and its implications in metabolic syndrome. The literature searches encompassed PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science databases, utilizing the keywords “pericyte”, “hyperglycemia”, “metabolic syndrome”, “molecular mechanisms”, “oxidative stress”, “inflammation” and “angiogenic imbalance.” The search strategy prioritized articles published between 2000 and 2025 to capture recent advancements.

Eligibility criteria required that studies investigate pericyte function or dysfunction in hyperglycemic conditions within the framework of metabolic syndrome or diabetes, including type 1 and type 2 models. Studies were included if they addressed molecular pathways such as oxidative and nitrosative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, autophagy impairment, pro-inflammatory signaling (including NF-κB activation), and angiogenic regulation relevant to pericyte health. Both *in vitro* and *in vivo* research, as well as clinical investigations, were considered, provided they explored the relationship between pericyte alterations and microvascular complications in organs such as the retina, pancreas, and brain.

Exclusion criteria encompassed studies focusing solely on systemic metabolic changes without specific analysis of pericytes or their microenvironment, and research lacking adequate methodological detail or mechanistic relevance to pericyte pathology in the context of metabolic syndrome or diabetes.

Out of 35 publications – 22 were included in the review.

Results

Chronic hyperglycemia, such as in the case of metabolic syndrome and T1D and T2D, triggers a cascade of cellular and molecular imbalances that further lead to a progressive pericyte loss in microvascular beds, specifically remarked at the level of the retina, pancreas, and brain⁷. The existent histopathological studies performed on animal and human tissues, showed that the diminished pericyte coverage of the capillary walls seems to be a

⁶ Hayden M.R., Yang Y., Habibi J., Bagree S.V., Sowers J.R., Pericytopathy: oxidative stress and impaired cellular longevity in the pancreas and skeletal muscle in metabolic syndrome and type 2 diabetes, in: *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*, 2010, nr. 5, pp. 290–303.

⁷ Almaça J., Weitz J., Rodriguez-Diaz R., Pereira E., Caicedo A., The Pericyte of the Pancreatic Islet Regulates Capillary Diameter and Local Blood Flow, in: *Cell Metabolism*, 2018, vol. 27, nr. 3, pp. 630-644; Wang H.K., Huang C.Y., Chen Y.W., Sun Y.T., Hyperglycemia compromises the ischemia-provoked dedifferentiation of cerebral pericytes through p21-SOX2 signaling in high-fat diet-induced murine model, in: *Diabetes & Vascular Disease Research*, 2021, vol. 18, nr. 1, art. 1479164121990641; Otsuka K., Morita A., Kashiwara T., Nakahara T., Pharmacological depletion of pericytes induces diabetic retinopathy-like abnormal blood vessels in neonatal rat retina, in: *Experimental Eye Research*, 2025, vol. 251, art. 110243.

turning point, that may be noted prior to the onset of symptomatic vascular insult. This fact highlights the primary role of pericytes in early microvascular dysfunction⁸.

A series of different mechanisms are implied to characterize the causes of the pericyte loss. One of the pivotal mechanisms implicated is the overproduction of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS) in pericytes due to chronic hyperglycemia. This pro-oxidant state exceeds the capacity of cellular antioxidant defenses, that culminate in a mitochondrial damage, impaired autophagy, and activation of intrinsic apoptotic pathways. Therefore, the pro-oxidant state induces mitochondrial fragmentation, suppresses autophagic flux, and triggers cell death pathway activation, which culminate in apoptotic pericyte detachment from the capillary wall. Immunolabeling and three-dimensional confocal imaging studies of diabetic rodents and post-mortem human retina, all consistently show that loss of pericytes precedes the loss of microvascular density and capillary integrity⁹. Moreover, this is a robust indicator of future retinopathy progression¹⁰.

Inflammatory processes are also hyperactivated in the hyperglycemic state, with enhanced activity of nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B) and increased cytokine production of tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), and inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS)¹¹. Their overexpression causes pericyte damage directly and sustains a pro-inflammatory microvasculature that rise the cellular stress, accelerates the pericyte depletion, and diminish the vascular repair capacity¹².

Impaired angiogenic signaling, mainly through vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), has also been found to be a cause of pericyte dysfunction in hyperglycemia. Overexpression of VEGF disrupts the stabilizing interactions between pericytes and endothelial cells that are vital for microvascular integrity. Meanwhile this cause microvascular leakage, pathological angiogenesis, and eventual capillary rarefaction in sensible tissues such as the retina. Time-dependent relationship between VEGF expression and pericyte loss illustrate the multidimensional effect of chronic hyperglycemia on vascular stability¹³.

From a mechanistic perspective, pericyte injury is interdependently correlated to altered mitochondrial homeostasis and dysregulated autophagy. Ultrastructural and genetic studies have recently elucidated that mitochondrial fragmentation, loss of membrane poten-

⁸ Nwadozi E., Rudnicki M., Haas T.L., Metabolic Coordination of Pericyte Phenotypes: Therapeutic Implications, in: *Frontiers in Cell and Developmental Biology*, 2020, vol. 8, art. 77; Simmonds S.J., Grootaert M.O.J., Cuijpers I. et al, Pericyte loss initiates microvascular dysfunction in the development of diastolic dysfunction, in: *European Heart Journal Open*, 2023, vol. 4, nr. 1, art. oead129.

⁹ Abdelazim H., Payne L.B., Nolan K. et al, Pericyte heterogeneity identified by 3D ultrastructural analysis of the microvessel wall, in: *Frontiers in Physiology*, 2022, vol. 13, art. 1016382.

¹⁰ Dabravolski S.A., Markin A.M., Andreeva E.R., Eremin I.I., Orekhov A.N., Melnichenko A.A., Emerging role of pericytes in therapy of cardiovascular diseases, in: *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 2022, vol. 156, 113928; Zhang Z., Huang Q., Zhao D., Lian F., Li X., Qi W., The impact of oxidative stress-induced mitochondrial dysfunction on diabetic microvascular complications, in: *Frontiers in Endocrinology (Lausanne)*, 2023, vol. 14, art. 1112363.

¹¹ Guo, Q., Jin, Y., Chen, X. et al. *NF- κ B in biology and targeted therapy: new insights and translational implications*, in: *Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy*, 2024, vol. 9, art. 53.

¹² Baker R.G., Hayden M.S., Ghosh S., NF- κ B, inflammation, and metabolic disease, in: *Cell Metabolism*, 2011, vol. 13, nr. 1, pp. 11-22.

¹³ Caldwell R.B., Bartoli M., Behzadian M.A. et al., Vascular endothelial growth factor and diabetic retinopathy: pathophysiological mechanisms and treatment perspectives, in: *Diabetes/Metabolism Research and Reviews*, 2003, vol. 19, nr. 6, pp. 442-455.

tial (MP), and downregulation of autophagy-related genes (e.g., Beclin-1 and LC3) result in impaired bioenergetic resilience, rendering pericytes incapable of mounting an adaptive response to metabolic stress¹⁴. This molecular stiffness constitutes the cornerstone of the transition between reversible pericyte malfunction and irreversible cell death, enhancing the tissue vulnerability to further hypoxic and ischemic insults¹⁵.

Table 1. Integrated mechanistic summary of the pericyte loss in hyperglycemia

Main mechanism	Key molecular players	Cellular/Pathological effect
Oxidative/Nitrosative Stress	ROS, RNS, mitochondrial fragmentation	Apoptosis, pericyte dropout
Inflammatory signaling	NF-κB, TNF-α, IL-1β, IL-6, iNOS	Cell stress, accelerated depletion
Angiogenic imbalance	VEGF overexpression, pericyte-endothelial uncoupling	Capillary leakage, neovascularization
Mitochondrial/Autophagic dysfunction	MP loss, ↓Beclin-1, ↓LC3	Loss of repair, energy deficit

Altogether, these pathobiochemical processes, OS, NS, inflammation, angiogenic imbalance, and mitochondrial-autophagic dysregulation, in unison induce sustained pericyte depletion and progressive microvascular dysfunction. In the retina, the loss of pericyte-endothelial crosstalk accelerates the onset of proliferative retinopathy, enhanced permeability, microaneurysm formation, and blood-retinal barrier breakdown¹⁶. At the level of the pancreas, it’s presented as a diminished islet perfusion and impaired peripheral insulin delivery, exacerbating glycemic dysregulation and progressive islet dysfunction¹⁷. Similarly, in the brain, cerebral pericyte loss facilitates blood-brain barrier permeability, augments neuronal susceptibility to metabolic insults, and is increasingly posited as an early event in diabetes-

¹⁴ Bharath L.P., Rockhold J.D., Conway R., Selective autophagy in hyperglycemia-induced microvascular and macrovascular diseases, in: *Cells*, 2021, vol. 10, nr. 8, p. 2114; Fu D., Yu J.Y., Yang S., et al., Survival or death: a dual role for autophagy in stress-induced pericyte loss in diabetic retinopathy, in: *Diabetologia*, 2016, vol. 59, nr. 10, pp. 2251–2261; Gong Q., Wang H., Yu P., Qian T., Xu X., Protective or harmful: the dual roles of autophagy in diabetic retinopathy, in: *Frontiers in Medicine (Lausanne)*, 2021, vol. 8, p. 644121.

¹⁵ Milani S.Z., Rezabakhsh A., Karimipour M., et al., Role of autophagy in angiogenic potential of vascular pericytes, in: *Frontiers in Cell and Developmental Biology*, 2024, vol. 12, p. 1347857.

¹⁶ Andrés-Blasco I., Gallego-Martínez A., Machado X., et al., Oxidative stress, inflammatory, angiogenic, and apoptotic molecules in proliferative diabetic retinopathy and diabetic macular edema patients, in: *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 2023, vol. 24, nr. 9, p. 8227; Yumnamcha T., Guerra M., Singh L.P., Ibrahim A.S., Metabolic dysregulation and neurovascular dysfunction in diabetic retinopathy, in: *Antioxidants (Basel)*, 2020, vol. 9, nr. 12, p. 1244.

¹⁷ Hayden M.R., Yang Y., Habibi J., Bagree S.V., Sowers J.R., Pericytopathy: oxidative stress and impaired cellular longevity in the pancreas and skeletal muscle in metabolic syndrome and type 2 diabetes, in: *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*, 2010, nr. 5, pp. 290–303.

associated cognitive decline¹⁸. All of these are central to the pathogenesis of microvascular complications in metabolic syndrome.

These pathomechanistic findings, presented in **Table 1**, collectively highlight that pericyte dysfunction and loss are not secondary consequences, but triggering events guiding the onset of microvascular complications in metabolic syndrome and diabetes. Recognition of the complex interplay between OS, inflammation, angiogenic disequilibrium, and perturbation of cellular homeostasis situates pericytes as early biomarkers and compelling therapeutic targets for prevention of diabetic microvascular sequelae. Further interventional trials to restore pericyte viability or address downstream molecular insults are likely to have profound impact on per-vascular disease burden management in metabolic syndrome.

Conclusions

Pericyte dysfunction emerges as a key driver of microvascular complications in metabolic syndrome and diabetes. Chronic hyperglycemia induces oxidative and nitrosative stress, mitochondrial damage, impaired autophagy, and inflammatory and angiogenic imbalances, leading to pericyte loss and microvascular instability. These changes precede and contribute to the development of complications in the retina, pancreas, and brain, highlighting the critical role of pericytes in maintaining vascular homeostasis.

Given their early involvement in disease progression, pericytes represent valuable biomarkers and promising therapeutic candidates. Targeting the underlying molecular mechanisms that compromise pericyte viability may offer new avenues for preventing or stopping diabetic microvascular complications.

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¹⁸ Yumnamcha T., Guerra M., Singh L.P., Ibrahim A.S., Metabolic dysregulation and neurovascular dysfunction in diabetic retinopathy, in: *Antioxidants (Basel)*, 2020, vol. 9, nr. 12, p. 1244.